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Formulation and evaluation of antimicrobial cream containing artocarpus heterophyllus lam

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Abstract:

Artocarpus heterophyllus Lam, which is commonly known as Jackfruit is a tropical fruit belonging to Moraceae family, is native to Western Ghats of India and common in Asia, Africa, and some regions of South America. It is known to be the largest edible fruit in the world. Jackfruit is rich in nutrients including carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, minerals, and phytochemicals. Several parts of Jackfruit tree including fruits, leaves, and barks have been extensively used in traditional medicine due to its anticarcinogenic, antimicrobial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, wound healing, and hypoglycaemic effects. The aim of this study was to investigate the antimicrobial effect of the leaves and show its therapeutic significance and application. The leaves were subjected to ethanolic extraction by maceration process and the resultant extract was used to formulate an antimicrobial cream that can be used to treat several bacterial and fungal infections of the skin

Keywords:

Antimicrobial cream, Formulation, Infection, Jackfruit.